

Missionary Strategies of Nigeria South-East Spiritans: The Application of New Methods of Evangelization; 1970-2020

Joseph Oguejiofor Okafor, PhD

Dept. of History and International Studies,
Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria.
Phone: +234-8064421 122; Email: okaforjog@hotmail.com

Abstract

Between 1885 and 1970, expatriate Missionaries of the Congregation of the Holy Spirit (Spiritans) engaged in what was judged by many as a successful missionary activity in the former Eastern Nigeria. Many have equally argued that their successes in Eastern Nigeria were as a result of their missionary strategies. With the exit of these Missionaries from Nigeria in 1970, the Spiritan missionary baton in this part of the globe fell on their few indigenous members of the Province of Nigeria South-East, who then, could boast of missionary presence in only six communities and only in Nigeria. This situation came at a time when the Catholic world was beckoning more on 'new evangelizing methods and expressions. By the end of 2019, members of this Province had missionary presence in two hundred and twenty-six communities in forty countries all around the world. Considering the instrumentality of strategies to the success of missionary activity, this paper, in descriptive/narrative and thematic approaches, tried to see to what extent the members of the Spiritan Province of Nigeria South-East employed the 'new methods of evangelization' in their missionary activity between 1970 and 2020. The findings show that amidst the wind of change in the world, they were able to adapt and profitably use functional and serviceable new methods of evangelization to spread their mission in the world.

Key words: Missionary strategy; New methods; Spiritans; Application

Introduction

Every mission that there is, targets achieving a goal. If such a goal is to be attained, the strategy for achieving it is a very crucial factor. As expressed in the *Notes et documents relatifs à la vie et à l'œuvre du Ven. Libermann (Notes and Documents relating to the life and work of Ven. Libermann; N.D. XII, 170 & N.D. II, 241)* and in the revised Rule of the Congregation of the Holy Spirit (Spiritans), the mission purpose of the Congregation in the Church states that;

The evangelization of the "poor" is our purpose.... Therefore we go especially to peoples, groups and individuals who have not yet heard the message of the Gospel or who have scarcely heard it, to those whose needs are the greatest, and to the oppressed We also willingly accept

tasks for which the Church has difficulty in finding workers. (Congregation of the Holy Spirit, 2013)

An international Catholic missionary religious Order, the Congregation of the Holy Spirit, founded by Claude Poullart des Place in 1703, was in 1848, merged with the Society of the Immaculate Heart of Mary, founded by Father Francis Libermann, with the union retaining the Congregation of the Holy Spirit as its name (Koren, 1983). Its failures or successes in the over 300 years of its missionary life, resulted basically from the various strategies applied by its members in pursuit of their mission objectives. Spiritan missionaries of European extraction arrived Onitsha, Nigeria on December 5, 1885 and engaged in what many considered a successful missionary activity until these expatriate missionaries were expelled from Nigeria in February 1970, as an aftermath of the Nigeria/Biafra war (Okafor, 2013). Whatever was their success, it was achieved by employing certain missionary strategies, especially charity works, proselytization, Christian village practice, education apostolate, health services, among others. With the exit of these expatriate missionaries, the indigenous members of the Congregation, Province of Nigeria South-East, relatively steering their own affairs, have currently sailed the Spiritan missionary boat world over. They have equally recorded ample successes, encouraged by adopting and applying, not only some worthwhile strategies of their predecessors, but also by applying “new methods of evangelization”.

In the Congregation of the Holy Spirit, ecclesiastical administrative jurisdictions grouping members within a certain geographical area, such as a country or region, is regarded as a ‘circumscriptions’. They are currently accorded the status of a Group, a Foundation, or a Province depending on their size and membership. The Province of Nigeria South-East (the Province) as a circumscription, covers the territories of the former Eastern Region of Nigeria. With its 2019 living membership statistic at five hundred and forty-seven (547) priests, Deacons, Brothers, and senior seminarians (NSE Provincial Report, August 2019), it is currently, the leading circumscription in the entire Congregation in terms of indigenous membership and the supply of personnel for the missions of the Congregation (C.S.Sp. 2019 General Statistics). Considering the relevance of strategies to the success of missionary activity, and conscious of this leading role and the fact of the Catholic Church’s emphasis on ‘New Evangelization’ in the period under review, the interest of this article rests squarely on revealing how much the members of the Province have employed some of the ‘new methods of evangelization’ in their mission areas all over the world. This is more

expedient when one considers that practically, very little or nothing is in prints concerning the missionary strategies of the Congregation in this part of the world, in comparison with the so much literature that exists on the same topic and subject in the period before 1970 (Okafor, 2013). The choice of the periodization scope of this paper, 1970-2020, was intended to mark the golden jubilee (50 years) the baton of the successful missionary enterprise of the expatriate Spiritan missionaries in Eastern Nigeria fell to their indigenous colleagues.

The Idea of ‘New Evangelization’

Following the considerations of the Council Fathers at Vatican II, as found especially in the documents, *Ad gentes divinitus* (December 7, 1965) and *Gaudium et spes* (December 7, 1965), Pope Paul VI, echoed in his Encyclical letter, *Evangelii Nunciandi*, what he already told the College of Cardinals in June 1973, restating that;

The conditions of the society in which we live oblige all of us therefore to revise methods, to seek by every means to study how we can bring the Christian message to modern man. For it is only in the Christian message that modern man can find the answer to his questions and the energy for his commitment of human solidarity. (Paul VI, 1975)

The Council Fathers and the Pontiff were conscious of a changing world and world views, and the inefficiency of some evangelizing approaches that had necessitated a revision of methods, so as to make good the evangelizing mission of the Church. Emphasizing further on this idea, Pope John Paul II, as cited in Synod of Bishops (2012), advised that; “The commemoration of this half of the millennium of evangelization will achieve its full meaning, if as bishops, with your priests and faithful, you accept it as your commitment; a commitment, not of re-evangelization, but rather of a new evangelization; new in its ardour, methods and expression.” The issue was thus seen as a call for ‘new evangelization’. In concretising the idea, therefore, the Bishops explained the demands of ‘new evangelization’, suggesting that;

The duty of the new evangelization compels the Church to examine the way Christian communities both live and bear witness to the faith today. In doing so, the new evangelization now becomes discernment or the ability to read and decipher the new sectors which have emerged in human history... so that, in turn, they might be turned into places for proclaiming the Gospel and experiencing the Church. (Synod of Bishops, 2012)

Taking from the above, ‘new evangelization’ which is the ‘proclamation of the Gospel’ and ‘experiencing the Church’, emanating from new experiences in human history, implies new methods of proclaiming and of expressing the Gospel. Foreseeing such methods and expressions, Paul VI emphasized that;

... evangelization would not be complete if it did not take account of the unceasing interplay of the Gospel and of man's concrete life, both personal and social. This is why evangelization involves an explicit message, adapted to the different situations constantly being realized, about the rights and duties of every human being, about family life without which personal growth and development is hardly possible, about life in society, about international life, peace, justice and development- a message especially energetic today about liberation. (Paul VI, 1975)

In an understanding of the above views, some of these ‘new’ methods and expressions of evangelization that draw one’s attention here include Acculturation and Inculturation; the practice of Basic Christian Community (BCCs); the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs); and the pursuit of Justice, Peace and Integrity of Creation. It is not that these approaches to evangelization are completely new to the Church, but that more emphases were laid on them in recent years. As missionaries, the members of the Province of Nigeria South-East were conscious of these methods and expressions in evangelization and did employ them in their missionary activity during the period under study.

Employment of New Methods of Evangelization

Acculturation and Inculturation

Acculturation and Inculturation became much emphasized in evangelization since after Vatican II Council. Both concepts are affiliated to culture. In *Gaudium et spes* (1965, 44), the Council Fathers drew attention to the Church’s experience from inculturation in the Greco-Roman world; and Paul VI (1975, 18-20) emphasized on the evangelization of cultures. From the point of view of the evangelization of cultures, one can talk here of acculturation and inculturation.

Olikenyi (2001), taking from Roest-Crollius, denotes acculturation as “encounter between cultures and ensuing cultural changes.” The character of acculturation is one of give and take. Culture as a way of thinking; a way of understanding and perception; and a way of living, defines

a people's belief and behaviour. On the other hand, inculturation, according to P. Arrupe, as quoted in Udoiidem (1996), is seen as:

The incarnation of Christian life and of the Christian message in a particular cultural context, in such a way that this experience not only finds expression through elements proper to the culture in question ... but becomes a principle that animates, directs and unifies the culture, transforming it and remaking it so as to bring a 'new creation'.

In other words, inculturation implies getting the gospel message of Christ integrated and expressed in a people's way of perception and life. Nonetheless, the definition of inculturation by Pope John Paul II as quoted in Olikeyi (2001), fits in appropriately to the merger of the two concepts of acculturation and inculturation. There, inculturation is defined as "the incarnation of the gospel (goodnews) in autochthonous cultures, at the same time, the introduction of those cultures into the life of the Church." This definition of inculturation reflects both the notion of acculturation and inculturation earlier defined. For the purpose of this work, therefore, the application of the two approaches in the evangelizing work of the missionaries of the Province of Nigeria South-East will be interchanged.

Generally, wherever these missionaries worked, they tried to understand its culture in order to enable smooth communication and relations with the people. Assimilation of cultural practices and meanings to be probably used in the expression of the gospel message becomes possible in this process. One of the missionaries of the Province, Father (Fr.) Collins Obiezeani, told of how, for instance, in the parish of St. Joseph, Keduoguo, Senegal where he worked, certain local rites for initiation were adapted in the conferment of the Sacrament of Baptism (Interview, 16/02/2018). Fr. David Atuanya similarly recalled how in Papua New Guinea mission, while appearing to minister to the public, they had to wear around their heads, dried "birds of paradise" with their feathers. In this culture:

When someone wears that, it indicates that the person is a 'big man' and, therefore, should be listened to. Jesus Christ is taken to be a 'big man' and the priest, when ministering, represents Jesus Christ. Thus, while ministering, he should wear the "bird of paradise" and that will make people pay heed to him and what he says. (Atuanya, Interview, 19/11/2017)

Different strokes for different folks, they say. While in Nigeria South-East and in the Catholic Church generally, the people stand up to listen to the Gospel proclaimed, the missionaries had the people rather seated when proclaiming it to the Shona people in Zimbabwe, since

culturally, their audience sits as a mark of respect and attentiveness when an elder is talking, and Jesus speaking in the Gospel as well as the priest here proclaiming it, are elders (Fr. John Asomugha, 25/05/2015).

Adaptation of various cultural practices was experimented by many other members of the Spiritan Province of Nigeria South-East. In fact, in the seminaries of the Province, the use of decent and noble cultural symbols and practices were encouraged. Fr. Anthony Ekwunife, as the Director of the Holy Ghost Novitiate, Awo-Omamma back in 1978, was known to have brought an *Akwu na-eche enyi (Igba Eze)* group of drummers and dancers, who taught their drumming and dance steps to the seminarians in the Novitiate. One finds that some of these cultural practices and rituals that formerly, some erroneously looked at as fetish, gradually became Christianised. Today, liturgical procession with *Igba Eze* dance is well adapted especially in the Catholic Church in Igboland. One would say that acculturation of practices and values that have typically nothing against the teachings of Christ, have succeeded in keeping many people united with the fold of Christ and with the Church where otherwise, such persons may have been alienated. It equally offered room to assimilate and understand better the real content of the message of the gospel as people express their faith in ways that it makes more meaning to them.

Basic Christian Communities (BCCs)

Another strategy employed by most missionaries of the Province of Nigeria South-East was that of the Basic Christian Communities (BCCs). The BCCs imply bringing Christians into small groups, often times made up of very few persons or families who share something in common, or who reside in the same area. It is also referred to as mini-parishes, life-communions, neighbourhood churches, and grass-roots communities (Okafor, 2019). The BCC has been defined as, “homogeneous groups of Christians who share common interests, values, and objectives; who search to emphasize primary, inter-personal, ongoing relationships; and who view themselves as ecclesial entities.” (Basic Christian Communities, 2003). The current idea of BCCs has its origins in the 1960s and has come to be practised in many places.

Fr. Obiezeani (16/02/2018), said that where he worked in Keduoguo, Senegal and in the parish of Saint Notre Dame de la Misericorde, Koundara, Guinea, Christians were organised as such in smaller groups where they met and discussed and viewed things affecting them from Christian perspectives. In many other missions of the members of the Province, including in the

Congo, in French Guyana, in Zimbabwe, among others, such practices were common. In BCCs, small communities, generally shared their concerns together mostly on weekly intervals and the priests came around at certain intervals to minister to them and offer pastoral help. The BCCs offered the elderly, the marginalized of the society, and those who reside far away from the parish centre, a reasonable opportunity to be part of the Church.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

The Church is basically living in a changing world. Pope Paul VI (1975) rightly thought in that direction when he averred that; “Our century is characterized by the mass media or means of social communication, and the first proclamation, catechesis or the further deepening of faith cannot do without these means....” It is not surprising that the Spiritan missionaries from the Province of Nigeria South-East adapted methods of evangelization to those of the changing world, especially the application of information and communication technologies (ICT). Members of the Province employed various ICTs to bring home their message of the Gospel to people at different times and places. Fr. Augustine Onyeneke recalled how some of the members of the Province moved from centre to centre in the 1970s and 1980s with cinema gadgets, with which they showed people documented films based on the Gospel. He remarked that in each place they went, many people were found to gather in the arena, including non-Christians. And often times way beyond the number of Catholics in the centre. He averred that the cinema shows usually left a great impact on the peoples (Okafor, 2019).

Other ICT methods employed by the members of the Province in evangelization included the use of radio and television programmes, the use of recorded messages in cassettes and plates, the production and circulation of gospel music, among others. In recent times, an aspect of ICTs employed profitably in evangelization by members of the Province is the internet. Some disseminate their reflections and teachings through the web. Fr. Ernest Munachi Ezeogu, a Scripture scholar from the Province, was very famous for his homily site located then at <http://munachi.com>. His site was patronised across countries, continents and races. Fr. Calistus Ofor also evangelized through his site; <https://www.myfaithmypride.com>; and Fr. Fidelis through <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCm4ccWaDsOiuurvaBQnLZdyw>. With the social media becoming very prominent, especially *WhatsApp*, many members equally resorted to it for evangelization purposes. No doubt, the use of the web and social media made it very easy for

people to be evangelized even in the comfort of their rooms and offices, notwithstanding that internet and social media facilities were unavailable to many, especially in very rural areas. Generally, the employment of various aspects of information and communication technologies has tremendously helped the members of the Province in evangelization.

Justice, Peace, and Integrity of Creation (JPIC)

Community Organizing, Advocacy and Empowerment

The mission of the Church is greatly concerned with ‘Integral Human Development’. This concern was popularized by Pope Paul VI’s *Populorum Progressio* (1967), his Encyclical on ‘the Development of Peoples’. His successors, John Paul II (1987, 1991, 1995), Benedict XVI (2009, 2011), and Pope Francis have left multiple texts that have furthered the popularity of Integral Development. In response to this concern, missionary religious bodies established an evangelizing organ called Justice, Peace and Integrity of Creation (JPIC). JPIC underscores the idea that;

...there is a certain order that leads to development. If there is respect for creation, if attention is given to justice and efforts are made to maintain peace, then development will be the result. This implies that if there is disorder, abuse of creation, injustice and a lack of peace, there will be a lack of development. (Missiaen, accessed, 13/05/2018)

The Congregation of the Holy Spirit commenting on its JPIC activities, states that its members have two-pronged models. It explains that they:

...adopt a two-pronged model of JPIC namely, Charity and Justice. In Charity, we are present pastorally and assist in poverty alleviation, render humanitarian assistance, assist refugees and migrants, and advance an integral and holistic ecology. In Justice, we advocate, support and defend the weak. We engage intergovernmental bodies to create people centered policies, respect the rights of women and minorities, commit ourselves to poverty alleviation, education, and assist in peacebuilding and the reconstruction of post-conflict societies. (<https://spiritanroma.org/jpic>)

Following these models, the members of the Province of Nigeria South-East approach JPIC activities through four channels: Community Organizing, Advocacy, Empowerment and Charity. Here, ‘community organizing’ refers to the practice of the missionaries motivating the people into taking positive actions in their life as individuals or as a community. ‘Advocacy’ refers to the situation whereby, missionaries as individuals or groups, approach individuals, companies, parastatals, institutions or governments to convince such to intervene positively in the life of

persons, groups, or people among whom they work. ‘Empowerment’ on the other hand, refers to creating an environment for, or providing the means for persons or people to pursue or achieve a set out goal (Okafor, 2019); while charity works here imply giving support to people in cash or kind. Members of the Province of Nigeria South-East were found to have applied these methods in various degrees at their places of mission engagements during the period under review.

In community organizing, members of the Province were found to have organized awareness talks, seminars, campaigns and classes for the purpose of conscientising communities and individuals on how to chart ways forward in certain conditions that might have constituted hindrances in their lives. For instance, Fr. Martin Okafor-Ilozue (Interview, 30/01/2019), told of how in the Philippines, he was able to motivate the people of Pindungangan in Barangay Tipanoy (Tipanoy Municipality) into building a nursery primary school for their children in 2007. The author also witnessed Fr. Goddy Odigbo in 2009, motivate Isuaniocha Catholic Community in Awka-North Local Government Area of Anambra State, to sand-fill the major access road to the town. There were so many other instances.

Concerning advocacy, there were members of the Province who were able to persuade individuals, agencies, companies and governments to provide social amenities and succour to many persons and people. In early 1980s, members of the Province who were on mission in Ebenebe, Awka-North, Anambra State, helped to get a temporary bridge done across their river (Fr. James Okoye, Interview, 05/01/2015). Again, in 2009, Fr. Okafor-Ilozue (Interview, 30/01/2019), while in the Philippines, convinced Hon. Michael Ralota, the Captain of Barangay T. Padilla, Cebu, to donate an office and classrooms in the Barangay building, used in giving positive orientation and skill acquisition to street children and children from poor families. Through his intervention also, Mayor Mike Rama of Cebu City, gave scholarships to thirty-five (35) children annually for six years, beginning from 2010. Added to these, the Spiritan International School of Theology, Attakwu, led by Fr. Gregory Olikenyi, got the former Governor of Enugu State, Sullivan Chime, to grade and prepare for tarring, the access road from Enugu-Port Harcourt expressway into Attakwu through the Seminary. This is to mention but a few.

Empowerment as an evangelizing strategy was used by members of the Province in many of their missions. Education is primarily a great measure of empowerment. They used vocational and conventional education as a strategy for evangelization, intended to empower people. A typical example was the establishment, between 1978 and 1980, of a primary school and St. Peter’s

College at Toto Parish, Nasarawa State by the members of the Province, targeted at enlightening the Bassa people of the area, and to provide them with new opportunities in life (Dike, 1999).

There were other measures of empowerment achieved by these missionaries. Madam Bernice Wagbara nostalgically narrated that

The people of the old Ubima catholic Parish will not forget in a haste, the love and great concerns of the Holy Ghost Fathers who worked in the mission, for the progress and poverty alleviation of the people. It was such concern that made the late Father Godwin Nnamani, C.S.Sp. to provide a garri processing house and machine for the women of the parish, and this made life and business easier and more profitable. (Wagbara, 04/07/2018)

While in Toto, Fr. Peter Dike was also known to be using his Pick-up and Peugeot J5 vehicles to lift Bassa people and their farm produce from the bush to the various markets, just to help them attend more favourable markets, and get better returns for their labour. Missionaries from the group who worked in places like Gokwe in Zimbabwe, Solwezi in Zambia, Borana in Ethiopia, among others, had similar stories to tell (Okafor, 2019). These missionaries were devoted to uplifting the life of the peoples among whom they worked.

Charity works were organized from time to time, practically in all the communities of the members of the Province. In some cases, it involved raising fund to provide accommodation for the homeless; or extending water supply to neighbours; or visiting the destitute, prison inmates, or occasionally sharing gifts to the less privileged especially at festival periods.

The effort of the members of the Province in JPIC execution did not go unnoticed as some of their members were appointed to high offices in national and international levels. Fr Chika Onyejiuwa was in November 2014, appointed the Executive Secretary of Africa-Europe Faith and Justice Network (AEFJN) with headquarters in Brussels. The AEFJN was founded to promote fairer economic relations between Africa and the European Union (<https://spiritanroma.org/aefjn-africa-europe-faith-and-justice-network/>). Similarly, Fr. Jude Nnorom was the General Coordinator of JPIC in the worldwide Congregation of the Holy Spirit from September 2014-2019. Fr. Vitalis Anusionwu was in 2018, made the National President of JPIC in Nigeria (overseeing JPIC activities of all the Catholic Religious Congregations in Nigeria). To all intent and purposes, the JPIC actions by the members of the Province brought the message of gospel closer to the peoples the encountered.

Prayer and healing ministry apostolate

Prayer and healing ministry proves to be another powerful new method of evangelization and apostolate engaged by the Spiritan members of the Province of Nigeria South-East in their missions. One of the most famous expatriate Holy Ghost missionaries that worked in the former Eastern Nigeria before 1970, was Fr. Denis T. O’Keefe. A roving preacher, he went round the missions holding prayers, retreats, and reconciling peoples; and in the effort to liberate them from ‘paganism’, encouraged them to surrender their charms and articles for traditional religious worships to him. He could be said to have introduced some element of prayer and healing ministry in Eastern Nigeria. However, his method seems quite different when compared to contemporary prayer and healing ministry apostolate in Nigeria. His method was basically aligned to retreats and to preaching as much as the stipulations of pre-Vatican II could allow.

Prayer and healing ministry is not peculiar to the Catholic Church. It is even difficult to exactly define what contemporary prayer and healing ministry is. However, one can try to give a picture of what prayer and healing ministry is among the Catholic fold in Nigeria. It refers primarily to Eucharistic adoration blended with “the employment of charismatic and certain Pentecostal modes of worship in a pastoral approach intended to assuage the spiritual, psychological, and physical needs of the faithful” (Okafor, 2019). This is not an expert opinion. It is left to experts in the field of religious study to arrive at an agreeable definition anyway. It is based on the above understanding that it is considered here as among new methods of evangelization employed by the members of the Province of Nigeria South-East. Late Fr. Godwin Ikeobi of Onitsha Archdiocese who began the Tuesday Prayer Group that had its root in an encounter he had with a childless woman at Nnewi in 1973 (Ikeobi, 1985) is generally seen as the pioneer of the contemporary prayer and healing ministry in the Catholic Church within the boundaries of the Province of Nigeria South-East. However, the fact remains that Fr. Ikeobi’s method was more conservative than charismatic. It is, therefore, not out of place to state that the contemporary prayer and healing ministry method of evangelization in Nigeria was popularized by a member of the Spiritan Province of Nigeria South-East; Fr. Emmanuel M.P. Edeh, and since his debut, the method has served many missions of the Province within and outside Nigeria.

Fr. Edeh was posted to the Holy Ghost Novitiate, Awo-Omamma in 1984. Certain of his pastoral encounters with people there were reported to have brought miraculous healings to some of those people. Soon, the quiet environment of the Novitiate compound became regularly

besieged by numerous people who came looking for Fr. Edeh, for healing and solutions to their problems. Unable to control the situation, the Provincial Administration of the period relieved Father Edeh of his appointment in the Novitiate and posted him to a parish environment at Elele. Unlike Fr. O’Keefe, the roving preacher, Fr. Edeh acquired land at Elele and developed it into a pilgrimage centre. People troop to the centre for counselling, healing (spiritual and physical), reconciliation of different sorts, miracles, and testimonies. Though Pentecostal prayers and songs were also used in the Centre, the greater focus of the Pilgrimage Centre was the regular and continuous adoration of Jesus Christ in the “Blessed Sacrament” and the recitation of traditional Catholic prayers, especially the Holy Rosary prayer. The pilgrims were encouraged to rather take their problems to Jesus Christ in the “Blessed Sacrament”.

The Elele pilgrimage centre soon became a “Jerusalem” of sort. On daily and on monthly basis, countless number of Christian pilgrims; Catholics and non-Catholics, besieged the Centre. Its “pilgrimage week” held usually on the first weekend of every month attracted and continues to attract many thousands of worshipers. Eke (2006), appraising the Centre, wrote:

Like the early Church ... the Catholic Prayer Ministry has witnessed an outpouring of the Holy Spirit and seen miracles of conversion and grace among God’s people. It has contributed immensely to the general growth of Christianity in the country and acted as a challenge to the main-line Pentecostal churches that prey upon many Catholic adherents.

In the history of the centre, several Cardinals and Bishops have participated in its activities. The then Apostolic Pro-Nuncio in Nigeria, Archbishop Carlo Maria Viganò, who presided over the 10th Anniversary celebration of the Centre in 1994, extolled the Centre before the mammoth crowd that gathered, saying that Fr. Edeh’s “work at Elele can be seen as one such fruit of the Spirit at work in the Church.” (Eke, 2006). On the Silver Jubilee Anniversary celebration of the Centre, the Catholic Church authority in Nigeria raised the centre to a National Pilgrimage Centre.

Emphasizing on the need for ‘new evangelization’, Pope Paul VI (1975) did note that; “One finds among the people particular expressions of the search for God and for faith.... These expressions were for a long time regarded as less pure and were sometimes despised, but today they are almost everywhere being rediscovered.” Such particular expressions found in prayer and healing ministry centres evidently resonate traditional Nigerian and African fulfilling expressions in worship which for long and until the Vatican II Council, was not accommodated by the Church’s liturgical rules. Their rediscovery and seeming success at the Catholic Prayer Ministry of the Holy

Spirit Elele have inspired many Catholic clergy and faithful to popularize what has become known as prayer and healing ministry. Since then, many other members of the Province have engaged in prayer and healing ministry as a method of evangelization, and the Provincial Administration gives its support to this evangelization strategy. The 2011 Chapter of the Province agreed that a Healing Ministry Committee be set up with responsibilities including to “Encourage and direct Spiritans who feel called to this important ministry” (Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria South-East, 2011). Evangelization through prayer and healing ministry as employed by the members of the Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria South-East proved greatly impactful in the missions it has been practised. It resulted to making many converts through it, many who seemed to have lost hope found hope and meaning in life. Some of the members who are seriously involved in prayer and healing ministry in their respective missions are listed in the table below.

Prayer and Healing Ministries founded by members of the Province of Nigeria South-East

S/No	Name of Prayer and Healing Ministry	Name of Founder	Location and Year Founded
1.	Catholic Prayer Ministry of the Holy Spirit	Fr. Emmanuel Edeh	Elele, Rivers - 1984
2.	Calvary Prayer Ministry	Fr. Peter Iwu	Okura, Kogi - 1997
3.	Holy Ghost Adoration and Restoration Ministry	Fr. Bartholomew Agu	Attakwu, Enugu – 2003
4.	Divine Grace and Mercy Adoration Ministry	Fr. Philip Ayika	Umuatugboma, Enugu- 2005
5.	Infant Jesus Pilgrimage Centre	Fr. Anthony Bruno Okeh	Obudu, Cross River – 2007
6.	Eternal Life Adoration Ministry	Fr. Henry Anyabuike	Ebe, Enugu - 2011
7.	Infant Jesus Adoration Ministry	Fr. Kingsley Ekwedigwe	Ehor, Edo -2013
8.	Holy Ghost Prayer Ministry	Fr. Richmond Obiano	Florida, Zimbabwe – 2011

Source: (Okafor, 2019)

Assessment

In the period under review, the members of the Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria South-East engaged in their evangelizing missions, often times applying new strategies and expressions. Among such strategies, acculturation/inculturation, BCCs, ICTs, JPIC and prayer and healing ministry were giving consideration in this paper. An assessment of the accounts given on these as they relate to the missionary work of members of the Province, indicate that the employment of some strategies was not widespread while some were. For instance, the use of the BCCs and ICTs were not regular in all the missions of the members but were rather used by a few. This may have been as a result of the general situation or practice in particular mission areas they found themselves. For instance, those who worked in very rural and poor communities, would find it hard to employ a good range of ICT in evangelization. For BCCs, it would have been difficult to implement such in areas like Igboland of Nigeria and major towns and cities all over the world. The fact remains that wherever these methods were applied, they proved very beneficial. As for the other strategies such as the Community Organizing, Advocacy and Empowerment activities of JPIC, the impact was ennobling, especially considering our today's world riddled by individualism and greed that marginalize the poor and the less informed. For instance, securing of thirty-five scholarships annually for six years in the area of Cebu, Philippines alone, would evidently bring tremendous societal transformation; lifting many out of poverty and associated societal vices.

For the contemporary evangelizing method of Prayer and Healing Ministry, one would admit that it was one gift the Spiritan missionaries of the Province bequeathed especially to Nigerians, with Fr. Emmanuel Edeh taking the lead. He became a household name and his ministry became unarguably, the pride of the Catholic Church in this part of the globe. Many hold the opinion that Fr. Edeh's ministry saved the Catholic Church in Nigeria and elsewhere from losing its members to the rising influence of Pentecostalism. The popularity of this ministry has spread to the point that even the Anglican Communion in Nigeria has adopted it in many places. Its success as a strategy has proved unbounded despite the few abuses that have been associated with it.

Conclusion

The discussion in this paper has so far shown that the members of the Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria South-East were not limited in their missionary activity, to the

strategies of their predecessors who evangelized Eastern Nigeria before 1970. Much more commendable, however, is their ability to positively respond to contemporary challenges of mission and the world by adapting new methods of evangelization other than those of their expatriate predecessors. From the study, apparently these strategies were functional and serviceable and so were able to lead to a tremendous increase in mission engagement by the Province. To have expanded the mission engagement of the members of the Province from six (6) communities and in only Nigeria in 1970 (Okafor, 2019), to mission presence in about two hundred and twenty-six (226) communities in forty (40) countries in all the continents of the world in 2019 (Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria South-East, 2020), is a proof that the works of the members were meaningfully valued, thus eliciting invitations from all quarters. Evidently, these missionaries were greatly able to adapt to changes in time, and more especially, in remaining docile to the promptings of the Holy Spirit which provided the directions in the midst of such changes. It is also a lesson to note that undue conservatism is unhealthy in missionary activity, and may retard success and growth. However, a major concern remains the depth of the training the missionaries receive in the seminaries, especially in the fields that would place them on a better footing to approach these new methods of evangelization and our changing world. This relates more importantly to the JPIC methods that may at times require some specialization. Suffice it to say, therefore, that contemporary missionary Congregations should develop further the curriculum of their seminaries to ensure that such concerns are better addressed.

References

- Basic Christian Communities. (2003). In *New Catholic Encyclopedia*. The Gale Group Inc. Retrieved September 21, 2018 from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/basic-christian-communities>
- Benedict XVI. (29 June 2009). *Encyclical Letter: Caritas in Veritate*. Retrieved March 19, 2019 From http://www.vatican.va/content/benedict-xvi/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_ben-xvi_enc_20090629_caritas-in-veritate.html
- (19 November, 2011). *Africae Munus: Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation*. Retrieved March 19, 2019 from http://www.vatican.va/content/benedict-xvi/en/apost_exhortations/documents/hf_ben-xvi_exh_20111119_africae-munus.html
- Congregation of the Holy Spirit. (2013). *Spiritual Rule of Life*. Roma: Scuola Tipografica S. Pio X.

- Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria, South-East. (2020). *2020 Spiritan Directory*. Onitsha: Spiritan Press.
- Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Province of Nigeria, South-East. (2011). *Chapter Decisions 2011*. Onitsha: Spiritan Publications.
- Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Rome. *AEFJN – Africa-Europe Faith and Justice Network*. Retrieved February 21, 2020 from <https://spiritanroma.org/aejfj-africa-europe-faith-and-justice-network/>
- Congregation of the Holy Spirit, Rome. *Justice, Peace and Integrity of Creation*. Retrieved February 21, 2020 from <https://spiritanroma.org/jpic>
- Dike, Peter O. and the Staff Editor. (June – Dec. 1999). The Spiritan Mission in Toto, Nigeria: -A Mission in Crisis. *The Missionary*, 4,2. (pp 3-7). Nsukka: Holy Ghost Fathers and Brothers.
- Eke, Casimir Iheanyi, C.S.Sp. (2006). *In the Footsteps of Our Founders: A History of the Spiritan Province of Nigeria, 1953 – 2002*. Onitsha: Spiritan Publications.
- Ikeobi, G.C. (1985). Catholic Responses to the Challenge of ‘Prayer Houses’ – Origin of the ‘Tuesday Prayer’ in Onitsha”. In V.A. Nwosu, (Ed). *The Catholic Church in Onitsha: People, Places and Events (1885-1985)*. (pp 262-275). Onitsha: Etukokwu Press Ltd.
- John Paul II. (30 December 1987). *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis*. Retrieved March 14, 2019 from http://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_jp-ii_enc_30121987_sollicitudo-rei-socialis.html
- (1 May 1991). *Centesimus Annus; Encyclical Letter*. Retrieved March 14, 2019 from http://www.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_jp-ii_enc_01051991_centesimus-annus.html
- (14 September, 1995). *Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation: Ecclesia in Africa*. Retrieved March 14, 2019 from http://w2.vatican.va/content/john-paul-ii/en/apost_exhortations/documents/hf_jp-ii_exh_14091995_ecclesia-in-africa.html
- Koren, Henry J. C.S.Sp. (1983). *To the Ends of the Earth: A General History of the Congregation of the Holy Ghost*. Pittsburgh: Duquesne University Press.
- Missiaen, Vic. [Integrity of Creation, Justice, Peace and Development](#). *Wajibu: A Journal of Social and Religious Concern*. 21. Retrieved March 27, 2018 from http://africa.peacelink.org/wajibu/articles/art_7513.html
- Okafor, Joseph Oguejiofor. (2013). *The Holy Ghost Congregation in the Spread of Catholicism in Igboland, 1885 – 1970*. (Unpublished MA Thesis). Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Okafor, Joseph Oguejiofor. (2019). *The Missionary activities of the members of the Holy Ghost Congregation, Province of Nigeria, South-East, 1970-2015* (Unpublished PhD Dissertation). Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Olikenyi, Gregory Ikechukwu C.S.Sp. (2001). *African Hospitality, A Model for the Communication of the Gospel in the African Cultural Context*. Nettetal: Steyler Verlag.

Paul VI. (March 26, 1967). *Populorum Progressio: Encyclical of Pope Paul VI on the Development of Peoples*. Retrieved March 10, 2019 from https://w2.vatican.va/content/paul-vi/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-vi_enc_26031967_populorum.html

----- (December 8, 1975). *Evangelii nuntiandi: Apostolic Exhortation of His Holiness Pope Paul VI to the Episcopate, to the Clergy and to All the Faithful of the Entire World*. http://www.vatican.va/content/paul-vi/en/apost_exhortations/documents/hf_p-vi_exh_19751208_evangelii-nuntiandi.html

Synod of Bishops; XIII Ordinary General Assembly. (2012). *The New Evangelization for the Transmission of the Christian Faith: Instrumentum Laboris*. Vatican City. http://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/synod/documents/rc_synod_doc_20120619_instrumentum-xiii_en.html

Udoiidem, S. Iniobong. (1996). *Pope John Paul II on Inculturation: Theory and Practice*. Lanham, Maryland.

Vatican II. (December 7, 1965). *Ad gentes divinitus*. In Flannery, Austin O.P. (Ed). (1981). *Vatican Council II: The Conciliar and Post Conciliar Documents*. 1981 Edition. (pp 813-856) Leominster: Fowler Wright Book Ltd.

----- Vatican II. (December 7, 1965). *Gaudium et spes*. In Flannery, Austin O.P. (Ed). (1981). *Vatican Council II: The Conciliar and Post Conciliar Documents*. 1981 Edition. (pp 903-1002) Leominster: Fowler Wright Book Ltd.